

EXAMINING BRICS MULTILATERALISM VIA A PERSPECTIVE OF THE 'BRICS PLUS' CONCEPT

Jagbir

UGC/NET (Qualified) in Political Science

Cite This Article: Jagbir, "Examining Brics Multilateralism Via A Perspective of the 'Brics Plus' Concept", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 75-

80, 2023.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, 2023 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

During the last two decades, the BRICS countries have placed a primary emphasis on collaboration on development. In particular, they have directed a significant amount of their efforts towards providing financial and technical help to the world's least developed nations. The views of the nations that make up the developing world are not heard nearly enough, and BRICS has the potential to become a crucial venue for them to do so. To some degree, the 'BRICS plus Model' offered a very helpful and open platform for developing nations, particularly for the LDCs, to take part in the global governance process. BRICS has a significant amount of credibility to discourse about the world, to provide answers, and to advocate certain ideas as reforms of the existing international global order as well. The development of multilateralism is a side effect of the democratisation of international organisations, particularly financial institutions. This study makes an attempt to find a correlation between the multilateral approach used by BRICS members and the notion of BRICS Plus. In addition, the paper discusses the many aspects that link the two notions and makes an effort to investigate the upcoming difficulties.

Key Words: International Politics, BRICS, BRICS Plus, Bretton Wood Institutions, Multilateralism

Introduction:

Most agree that the 21st century international order is multi-polar, particularly after the Cold War. Nations are working and embracing a win-win approach for mutual growth and international peace and security. Nations move towards global liberalism. Instead, world's economic core is migrating rapidly west to east. Among international governments, BRICS is becoming the new power hub. The five nations formed an international regime to gain mutual advantages and influence on international economic, financial, and political institutions. One fifth of global GDP and 42% of the world's population are BRICS nations. Their desire for mutually beneficial collaboration and respect unites them. BRICS foreign policy and 'BRICS plus' will continue to promote peaceful coexistence, collaboration, and negotiation to resolve conflicts. 'The BRICS Plus' will educate and establish a 'soft' regional cooperation strategy.

China invited Egypt, Kenya, Tajikistan, Mexico, and Thailand to the 2017 BRICS meeting, which focused on 'BRICS Plus'. Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi said, "The 'BRICS Plus' pattern is openness, inclusiveness, cooperation and mutual benefits, which is highly consistent with the BRICS spirit. The 'BRICS Plus' pattern aims to expand conversation and collaboration between BRICS nations and other emerging markets and developing countries, promote larger partnerships, and support large-scale joint growth and prosperity¹.

Although the concept is still in progress and shaped as reality. Despite the uncertainty of BRICS Plus concept, its basic Principles can be summarized as follows:

- Enhancing the integration whiting a group of developing countries for better stability and enhanced role in the world economy.
- Developing a comprehensive partnership that involves a broader agenda and goes beyond the discussion of trade and financial cooperation.
- Uncertainty in approaches provides an opportunity to create a completely new format of interaction that differs from classical models of economic integration and cooperation².

The worldwide system is readjusting drastically. Peace and progress are current. The need for global cooperation is growing. A new international order based on global interests is emerging. Joint global governance has been stressed, and "all-win" has given way to "zero-sum" in international relations. Emerging market nations that want greater growth space and established countries that want to preserve their advantage will clash in the next year. Containment and counter-containment will become structural contradictions³. Through the BRICS Plus Concept, BRICS Multilateralism can address all world issues.

Factors Which Connect BRICS Multilateralism with 'BRICS Plus':

BRICS is strengthening relations and cooperating with other nations, especially emerging and developing ones, as international and regional organisations in the spirit of openness, solidarity, and mutual assistance. The report argues that the BRICS analysed multilateralism as a new global order that emerges owing

to global socialisation and economic and political power moving to emerging nations. The BRICS Plus concept evolved from several reasons.

First, rising international standing on platform. The five countries also play a major role in leading international organisations and entities like the UN, G-20, G-77+China, Non-Aligned Movement, WTO Doha Round Negotiations, and regional associations like the CIS, CSTO, SCO, APEC, UNASURB, MERCOSUR, AU, SADC, and SAARC. The BRICS alliance has long promoted developing nations' interests in global organisations. It might be a global south "integrator" or "consolidator" in the present context. Consolidating economic and lobbying resources inside the international organisation is required to develop multi-polarity and remedy "underrepresentation". The 2017 Chinese BRICS Plus proposal, which needs participation and methods, is essential in this regard⁴. Such a support structure would help third-world nations flourish and meet their needs internationally.

Second, the BRICS nations' unified stance and influence during the financial crisis shows third-world countries how, despite their differences, they can find common ground and influence international trends. The BRICS framework and its challenges for Europe can only be understood in the context of growing numbers of influential emerging powers alliances and other multilateral frameworks in the Asia-Pacific region and the South⁵. Countries vary in endowment, industrial strength, and economic growth strategies. This provides strong complimentary linkages and a hopeful future for economic cooperation and trade agreements, particularly for developing nations. China, the "World's Workshop," has dense people resources and high energy and mineral demand. India has excellent computer and software sectors. Brazil's agriculture and livestock are developed. South Africa produces gold and platinum abundantly. Russia has abundant natural gas and oil, aerospace, and military sectors.

Third, their development is similar. BRICS countries face similar challenges as other emerging nations. For intense, building their economy, raising living standards, and generating employment. BRICS also wants Brattonwood Institutions democratised and decentralised. Cooperation among BRICS Plus may help build and sustain a cohesive viewpoint. A multilateral coalition of BRICS Plus countries in the WTO could help rebuild the institution by opposing rising trade protectionism from advanced economies and advocating for e-commerce and investment facilitation. Due to its close cooperation with the New Development Bank and AIIB⁶, the BRICS Plus Block may help shift the World Bank's agenda by expanding the use of the IMF's SDRs, increasing the set of reserve currencies, expanding their currencies from the basis for SDR valuation to include currencies of all major economies, and including GDP as a factor in currency selection for the SDR. BRICS Plus contact may focus on Bretton Wood Institution multilateral collaboration.

Table 1: IMF Quota and Voting Power of BRICS Countries

Countries	Quota		Voting	
	Millions of SDRs	% of Total	Numbers	% of Total
Brazil	11,042	2.32	111,879	2.22
Russia	12903.7	2.71	130,496	2.59
India	13114.4	2.75	132,603	2.63
China	30,482.9	6.40	306,288	6.08
South Africa	3051.2	0.64	314,71	0.63

Source: IMF (<http://imf.org.in>)

BRICS nations' IMF quotas and voting are shown in the table. Brazil's SDR quota is 11,042 million and 2.32% of the total. Russia, India, China, and South Africa have 2.72%, 2.75%, 6.40%, and 0.64% quotas. Also, BRICS nations vote less. Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa have 2.22%, 2.59%, 2.63%, 6.08%, and 0.63%. Analysing the quota and voting mechanism suggests that the institution needs the 'BRICS Plus'.

They support thorough Security Council reform. The UNSC has five permanent members, and developing nations desire democratic change. 'The most notable developing power bloc, the BRICS, built on UNSC reform and R2P. Both immediately target UNSC liberal policy and international authority. Thus, how the BRICS position themselves on these two problems partially answers the more general question of whether the liberal international order created after WW2 is threatened. UNSC is a purely intergovernmental organisation with highly centralised decision-making authority and rests firmly with states, which are in an uneven power relationship and must adapt to accommodate emerging nations⁷. The BRICS Plus want more permanent UNSC seats. Both BRICS permanent UNSC members can invoice them on Security Council Platform.

Four of the BRICS nations are from the global South, hence this organisation should promote south-south cooperation. Countries face new problems after the cold war. BRICS is a big worldwide platform for south-south cooperation to overcome issues. BRICS Plus supports the proposal since it advocates for developing nations in the global south. BRICS collaboration in the global south challenges the developed north. China's economic policy should be given more thought than dismissal due to the 2008 financial crisis created by the developed north. In their 2016 GOA Declaration, BRICS endorsed this method. Scholars also question if BRICS provide a distinct viewpoint than neoliberal Western nations. They say it maintains the global neoliberal system

instead of confronting it⁸. It is clear that south-to-south cooperation is not a guarantee in the current period of interstate, interregional free trade, but it may prosper. BRICS Plus intends to increase south-south cooperation, and BRICS can lead it.

International economy changed fundamentally in the recent decade. In contrast, emerging nations have significant infrastructural and sustainable development demands. To expand, 'BRICS Plus' requires massive infrastructural expenditures. The figures show that emerging and developing nations' GDP must rise from 0.8-0.9% to 1.8%-2.3 trillion by 2020. This contains \$200-300 billion and is climate-resilient. East Asia and Pacific (EAP) needs 45% of the annual infrastructure needs, Europe and Central Asia (ECA) 7.5%, Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) 8%, South Africa (SA) 23%, MENA 8.5%, and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) 8%. The development Bank and contingent reserve structure may benefit BRICS Plus. This Bank can greatly aid international, regional, and national development banks in networking. So they may form a chain to improve poor and emerging nations' financial and technical help.

BRICS nations dominate their continent. Brazil is a prominent South American nation. Russia represents Eastern Europe and Trans-Asia. However, India and China dominate Asia's economy. South Africa is among the most developed and economically-politically powerful African nations. Regional integrated accords focus on these continent's leaders serving other nations. Brazil in MERCOSUR, Russia in EAU, South Africa in SADC and SACU, India in SAARC and SAFTA, and China in ASEAN+1. The grouping leads international organisations and entities like the U.N., G-20, NAM, WTO Doha Round Negotiations, and continental associations like the CIS, CSTO, SCO, APEC, UNASURB, MERCOSUR, SAARC, SCO, BIMSTEC, and Russia. The new extended format may be made viable by a high-quality trans-regional agenda that meets current global economic development patterns, global issues, and the strategic objectives of a group of developing nations. Along with traditional trade and financial aspects of cooperation, e-commerce, inter-state cooperation for small and medium enterprises, and a BRICS Plus technological platform for developing states should be prioritised⁹. The trans-regional cooperation that benefits all developing and underdeveloped nations will succeed if the BRICS countries and its integration partners are interested in implementing the BRICS Plus idea. An alternative theoretical understanding of 'BRICS Plus' exists. BRICS Plus wants a worldwide shift from unipolar to bipolar or multipolar, as does the Balance of Power theory. The Constructive Theory emphasises power and the social role of participating nations in collaboration, which may lead to "some form of collective identity". The notion says BRICS collaboration is driven by a shared understanding of social roles and positions, objectives, and ways to success. Theory¹⁰ focuses on BRICS Plus. Regime Theory, BRICS fits this theoretical structure. The inaugural BRICS Summits' joint Statements and Declaration established the regime's principles and practises. Their function is similar to the solemn Declaration of the OPEC 1975, first Summit at Algiers. The BRICS papers created a multilateral diplomacy-based premise to develop 'a move democratic and fair multi-polar global order'¹¹. After the Cold War, "New-Trade Theory" addresses certain Neo-regionalism difficulties and provides new tools, but it is eclectic and does not provide a coherent framework for empirical study. Under global free trade, production and use of primary factors according to comparative advantage are win-win, with welfare benefits from efficiency¹². BRICS Plus is another example of New-regionalism.

Today, no global crisis can be solved without BRICS collaboration. The world's biggest problems-climate change, energy crises, food security, development assistance, safe nuclear energy for peaceful purposes, transnational players, etc.-are tied to BRICS. BRICS leaders criticised trade and investment impediments on 'green economy' development at the New Delhi Summit. The BRICS countries also recognise the need of completing the UN Millennium Development Programme by 2015, particularly by providing technical and financial assistance to disadvantaged states to implement development programmes and social protection for their populations.

BRICS also seeks to help its members battle drug trafficking, cyber terrorism, cyber crime, human trafficking, and maritime piracy. Experts think the BRICS countries may create a positive external environment for their growth by encouraging communication and cooperation on global hot spots including Mid and West Asia, Korean Peninsula, North and Mid Africa, Venezuela crisis, Dubai Sundown issue, etc. The BRICS will have a firm foundation for the future, and the 'BRICS Plus' idea gives emerging and new economies optimism on such concerns.

Challenges between BRICS Multilateralism and 'BRICS Plus Concept':

According to the evidence presented, the 'BRICS Plus' will have a stable foundation upon which to build their future. However, it is difficult to predict how the five nations will evolve in the years to come. There are a number of obstacles that must be overcome before the BRICS Plus idea can become a reality. To start, there are "internal differences." The BRICS nations each have a distinct history and culture, in addition to a distinct background. Some of them carry historical baggage, while others are in harmony with the current day. Regarding some political and security matters, as well as the establishment of strategic trust, they have positions that are rather different from one another. Additionally, due of the similarities in economic level, growth stage, and industrial structure, there is rivalry between the five nations in international commerce. Additionally, the

attempts of the five countries to obtain more energy, resources, and market share have led to some frictions¹³. These are the aspects of their relationship that can be changed by the other elements.

The term 'external constraint' refers to the second facet of their struggle. In this regard, the primary argument given by the many other emerging nations is that. Some developing nations are concerned that their preeminent position in the present alignment of global interests may be challenged by BRICS countries. As a result, these nations want to use every measures at their disposal to restrict and constrain the growth of BRICS cooperation. There is a rising level of mistrust among certain nations over the identity and nature of BRICS. They are afraid that since these nations have more interests and concerns in common with developed countries, they would "Quit the South and Join the North" and overlook the shared interests of the developing countries that they share with those countries. The BRICS face a number of challenges, the third of which is the building up of the group's institutions. Policy discussion and interactions have been the primary focal points of BRICS collaboration.¹⁴ Although there have been instances of practical collaboration in a number of different domains, such cooperation has only just begun and must be maintained. Concerning the subsequent stage, the BRICS nations need to steer clear of situations in which "much is said but little is done."

The BRICS + idea is also distinct from one another based on the principles of regionalism and multilateralism; however, in order to comprehend this, one must first have a firm grasp on the concepts of regionalism and multilateralism. The geographical breadth of one and the other organization's membership is the primary distinction between the two. The term "multilateralism" refers to collaboration between many nations or parties on a worldwide scale, while the term "regionalism" refers to the integration and cooperation between countries that are located within the same geographical area. The EU and the UNO are the best examples to comprehend the notion. The European Union (EU) is an example of regionalism, whereas the United Nations Organisation (UNO) is an example of multilateralism. When seen as a whole, however, BRICS is not without significance for the European Union and the stance it takes on multilateralism. Both in terms of their substance and their technique, the perspectives of the BRICS nations on multilateralism are distinct from those of the EU. The EU adheres to the regionalism idea and has implemented free trade agreements and a unified currency. On the other hand, BRICS does not share a single geographical territory and does not have any other mutual financial arrangements.¹⁵ Technically, BRICS is increasing its bounds via a programme called BRICS Plus, and it is leaning more towards multilateralism. Within the framework of the BRICS Plus idea, the five nations are not only linked with other nations in the area for the purpose of mutual cooperation, but they are also linked with the organisations of other regions. Having said that, under these circumstances, the ability of certain developing nations to accept the BRICS expansion hypothesis is diminished. Because the majority of nations in the third world have the impression that the BRICS group's primary objective is to build its own economy rather than the South-South Cooperation. They believe that just referring to it as a "economic cooperation regime" would not be enough; rather, significant progress towards becoming a "Union" similar to the EU will be required first.

The next obstacle is the concern that is being voiced by other nations, which asks, "Is there any Hidden Agenda of China in Promoting 'BRICS Plus'?" As was just said, the 'BRICS Plus Concept' will be presented to the other four countries in 2017 for consideration. E. Y. Arapova made the assertion that the academic community and the other five nations view the Chinese endeavour with a great deal of scepticism. The academic community in India, in particular, has come to the conclusion that the notion is nothing more than a tool that China may use to further its own economic and political goals, as well as to expand its sphere of influence on the regional, interregional, and global stages. Experts from India claim that China primarily urges only its key allies to participate in the discussion format, which, if true, has the potential to considerably weaken the Indian position¹⁶. It is also possible for it to change the voting pattern or the process of reaching mutual consensus on any topic owing to the influence that China has on members of the BRICS. New symmetrical order was established on the international arena after the conclusion of the cold war. China aims to disrupt the symmetry and challenge the monopoly that the United States has. To achieve this goal, China may use BRICS Plus as a tool in its arsenal to shape developments in international affairs.

BRICS Plus is an initiative that not only encourages the growth of the BRICS grouping but also extends membership invitations to other nations. However, it is not as easy as it may first seem. In his studies, William Daldegan noted that Brazil and India seem to have less of an interest in expanding their territory. A remark made by the Brazilian government during the 2019 Summit revealed that there are barriers standing in the way of Argentina's desire in joining the BRICS. In the case of India, the conflict stems from India's ideological differences with Pakistan. The expansion plan implicitly gives Pakistan, with which India has had a long-standing dispute along the border, the opportunity to pursue its own goals. India also presumed that the concept would be advantageous to Chinese interests in relation to the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC)¹⁷. It would seem that the BRICS nations, particularly Asian-India, Russia, and China, have made their "choice for multilateralism" when evaluating the different rising power alignments and multilateral frameworks in the Asia-Pacific area. This is the case when looking at the situation in the Asia-Pacific region. However, this is a decision that is founded on a completely other set of principles¹⁸. For

example, they place a higher priority on economic growth and development, and they do not want the economy to be constrained by worries about monetary troubles. Instead, they place a higher priority on environmental preservation, social protection, and human rights. On the other hand, if it concerns the institutions of Brattwood, then the aforementioned concerns become crucial in order to sustain their economy. To summarise, each of the five countries has a unique perspective on multilateralism.

Conclusion:

In the last section of this article, we covered how the notion of 'BRICS plus' might help the BRICS nations achieve their multilateralism goals. There are many additional instances that have proved that BRICS nations may collaborate with other countries and perform advantages for each other in areas that are mutually beneficial. The idea of BRICS Plus has the potential to become an important instrument in the process of providing economic and political access for developing and underdeveloped nations to the major global platforms. In the next years, BRICS plus has the potential to develop into a significant forum for changes in the Security Council, the IMF, and World Bank rates. It would act as an instrument for the progress of multilateralism, putting attention on the concerns of underrepresentation of emerging and developing nations in universal entities. This would help promote multilateralism. The nations that make up the BRICS group have the potential to bolster their position as a "gateway to Africa," so improving their ability to acquire valuable resources and contributing to the overall development of the African continent. The incorporation of additional members via the BRICS Plus initiative would make it feasible to broaden existing ties through the formation of bilateral as well as multilateral contacts across the majority of economic spheres. Despite the fact that there would be many obstacles to overcome, the BRICS Plus idea will have to be implemented in the actual world at some point. On the other hand, it is also true that in the realm of international politics, relations between nations have been making steady progress while facing a great deal of opposition. "BRICS plus" has the potential to become a more effective diplomatic effort, which will be critical to the success of the BRICS' multilateralism.

References:

1. Wang, Y. (2017), "BRICS Plus" pattern to fully Release Vitality of BRICS Cooperation, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China (Document). Access from http://www.fmpre.gov.cn/mfa_eng/zxxx_662805/t1489003.shtml/ . Retrieved on April 15, 2023.
2. Arapova, E. (2019), The 'BRICS Plus' as the First International Platform Connecting Regional Trade Agreements. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, Vol. 19, Issue 2, pp. 33-34. Access from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/343418118>. Retrieved on April 15, 2023.
3. Ibid.
4. Arapova, E.Y. & Lissovlik, Y.D., (2021), The BRICS Plus Cooperation in international Organization: Prospects for Reshape the Global Agenda, *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, p, 193. Access from <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/research/journals/apssr/2021-December-vol21-4/14-the-brics-plus-cooperation-in-international-organizations-prospects-for-reshaping-the-global-agenda.pdf> Retrieved on April 16, 2023.
5. Keukelerire, S. & Hooijmaaijers, B. (2013), The BRICS and Emerging Power Alliances and Multilateral Organization in the Asia-Pacific and Global South: Challenges for the European Union and its view on Multilateralism, *JCMS Publication*, p.6, DOI: 10.1111/jcms.12102. Retrieved on April 16, 2023.
6. Arapova, E.Y. & Lissovlik, Y.D. (December 2021), The BRICS Plus Cooperation in international Organization: Prospects for Reshape the Global Agenda, *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, p. 192. Access from <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/research/journals/apssr/2021-December-vol21-4/14-the-brics-plus-cooperation-in-international-organizations-prospects-for-reshaping-the-global-agenda.pdf> Retrieved on April 16, 2023.
7. Stehen, Mathew D. & Michael Zurn (ed.), *Contested World Order: Rising Powers, Non-Governmental Organizations and the policies of Authority beyond the Nation-State*, Oxford University Press, July 2019, p.169. DOI:10.1093/oso/9780198843047.0030005 Retrieved on April 29, 2023.
8. Diko, Nqiophisa & Sempijja, Norman (November, 2020), Does participation in BRICS foster South-South Cooperation? Brazil, South Africa and Global South, *Journal of Contemporary African Studies*, 24 November 2020, Vol. 39, Issue 1, p. 155, DOI: 10.1080/02589001/2020.1837746. Retrieved on April 29, 2023.
9. Arapova, E., (2019), The 'BRICS Plus' as the First International Platform Connecting Regional Trade Agreements. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, Vol. 19, Issue 2, p. 41. Access from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/343418118>. Retrieved on 1 April 15, 2023.
10. Ibid, p.44.
11. Zhang, W. and Li, Z.(2011), " The Rise of BRICS: Strategic Basis Cooperation Agenda and International Influence", *International Strategic Studies*, Vol.3, No.101, p.47.
12. Mary E. Burifisher, *Regionalism: Old and New, Theory and Practice*, International Food Policy Research Division, Washington, 2004, p.18.

13. Kund., P,(2014), BRICS: Challenge and Prospects, Centre for Budget and Governance Accountability, New Delhi, Access from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/306960040>. Retrieved on May 11, 2023.
14. Ibid.
15. Stephan, K. (2013), “ The BRICS and other emerging power Alliances and Multilateralism organizations in the Asia-Pacific and Global South: Challenges for the European Union and its view on Multilateralism”, Journal Common Market Studies, Vol. 52, Issue 3, p. 58. Access from <http://doi.org/10.1111/jcms/2102>. Retrieved on May 13, 2023.
16. Arapova, E. (2019), The ‘BRICS Plus’ as the First International Platform Connecting Regional Trade Agreements. Asia-Pacific Social Science Review, Vol. 19(2), p.34. Access from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/343418118>. Retrieved on April 15, 2023.
17. Daldegan, W.(2022), Opinion-Challenge for the Expansion of BRICS, E-International Relation, 2022, pp.1-2. Access from <http://www.e-ir.info/2022/06/09/opinion-challenge-for-the-expansion-of-the-brics/>. Retrieved from April 18, 2023
18. Keukelerire, S., & Hooijmaaijers, B. (2013), The BRICS and Emerging Power Alliances and Multilateral Organization in the Asia-Pacific and Global South: Challenges for the European Union and its view on Multilateralism, JCMS Publication, 2013, p.10, DOI:10.1111/jcms.12102. Retrieved from April 16, 2023.